

MEDICAL SCIENCES

AI-SUPPORTED DIGITAL HEALTH LITERACY: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

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ABSTRACT

Digital health transformation requires healthcare professionals not only to use digital tools but also to evaluate the data produced by these tools and Artificial Intelligent (AI)-supported outputs accurately, safely, and ethically. This study aims to reveal how the concept of digital health literacy can be restructured in the age of AI. Accordingly, studies published between 2015 and 2026 in the Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, and ERIC databases were searched using a scoping review approach. A total of 600 studies were assessed, 578 unique studies were examined, and 30 studies were included in the core analysis pool. As a result of the thematic synthesis, AI-supported Digital Learning Literacy was identified as a multilayered structure consisting of five domains: digital health systems literacy, AI literacy, data and information literacy, critical evaluation and use of decision support, and ethics, security, and privacy. The findings show that the ability to use digital systems is no longer sufficient for healthcare professionals; rather, they need to evaluate AI-generated outputs, the reliability of data, ethical risks, and their impact on clinical decision-making processes together. The AI-supported Digital Health Literacy framework developed in this study contributes to positioning healthcare professionals as conscious users, critical evaluators, and ethical decision-makers in digital and AI-supported healthcare services.

Keywords: Digital health literacy, AI literacy, healthcare professionals, digital health competencies, scope review.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, rapid and significant developments in digital technology have made a substantial transformation necessary in the field of healthcare. Technological advances such as electronic health records, big data analytics, clinical decision support systems, AI-supported diagnostic systems, and the integration of wearable Technologies into health systems have become visible within the scope of digital health [1]. The World Health Organization [2] defines digital health as the field of knowledge and practice associated with the development and use of digital Technologies to improve health. Digital health is known to offer several advantages, including providing patients with better and more direct information, supporting healthcare professionals in the diagnosis and treatment of patients, enabling verifiable and searchable records of health data such as births and deaths, and providing health managers with operational and strategic information [3]. However, digital health transformation should not be understood merely as a transformation of technological infrastructure; rather, new competencies related to digital health need to be developed [4].

Although core digital competency categories for healthcare professionals have been classified through different approaches in the literature [4; 5; 6; 7], they generally appear to constitute a multidimensional structure, particularly including digital health literacy, data management, and mobile application use from the foundation of digital health competencies; however, electronic health records, data documentation, and clinical decision support systems also directly enhance the quality of patient care through the large-scale data they provide [5; 6]. Nevertheless, the use of big data raises important questions regarding who owns the collected data, who controls and manages it, and how data pri-

vacy can be ensured [3]. These issues become particularly important when AI-based Technologies are used, indicating that digital health competencies need to be addressed from a broader and more complex perspective.

AI-supported applications are already being used in many healthcare processes, including risk scoring, image interpretation, clinical decision support systems, and the summarization of health records [8]. The growing importance of AI in healthcare has created a need for healthcare professionals to develop a comprehensive understanding of AI Technologies [9]. Although AI systems offer various advantages, they also raise several risks and concerns, including privacy, data security, algorithmic bias, and the need to evaluate ethical and legal implications [10]. From this perspective, it is critically important for healthcare professionals to possess not only technical knowledge but also the competence to understand the ethical implications of AI, its role in decision-making processes, and its limitations [8; 11]. In this context, AI literacy among healthcare professionals should be regarded as a necessity.

Long & Magerko [12] defines AI literacy as a set of competencies enables individuals to critically evaluate AI Technologies, communicate and collaborate effectively with AI, and use AI as a tool online, at home, and in the workplace. AI literacy is addressed across several dimensions, including understanding the structure and functional of AI technologies, critically evaluating and interpreting AI outputs, and developing ethical awareness in the use of AI [13]. Although different organizations and the broader literature provide general frameworks for AI literacy, it appears that a healthcare-specific AI competency framework has not yet been sufficiently addressed [11]. However, AI literacy is critically important not only for general technology use but also for the safe and effective use of AI applications

they are becoming increasingly widespread in healthcare services.

As the use of AI Technologies in healthcare continues to expand, the need for and interest in AI-related competencies are expected to increase. Recent studies indicate that, for healthcare professionals, AI literacy is not limited to the ability to use AI technologies; it also includes competencies related to understanding how AI works, recognizing its limitations, evaluating its ethical use, identifying algorithmic biases, and understanding its role in clinical decision-making processes [8; 9; 11]. However, these studies generally address AI literacy as a standalone construct and do not consider it together with digital health literacy.

The acceleration of digital transformation in healthcare and the growing use of AI applications is expanding the competencies expected of healthcare professionals. While conventional Digital Health Literacy (DHL) includes skills such as using digital systems accessing information, evaluating this information, and applying it in relevant decisions, AI-supported digital health systems require additional competencies, including understanding AI Technologies interacting with these systems, and critically appraising the outputs they generate. In this context, healthcare professionals need to draw on these two competency domains simultaneously. Therefore, digital health literacy and AI literacy should not be considered independent domains, but rather complementary competencies within the evolving field of digital health. Accordingly, DHL in the age of AI needs to be reconsidered through broader and more integrated dimensions. This study aims to reinterpret the framework of DHL in the age of AI and to propose a competency framework that healthcare professionals need to develop.

2. Method

This study was designed as a scoping review aimed at developing a conceptual framework for AI-supported DHL by integrating the literature on DHL and AI literacy. The scoping review approach is an appropriate method for mapping the existing literature in a specific research area and for identifying key concepts, types of evidence, trends, and gaps in the literature [14].

The literature search was conducted in the Scopus, PubMed, Web of Science, and ERIC databases. During the search process, the keywords “AI literacy”, “digital health literacy”, “health informatics competencies”, “health data literacy”, and “clinical decision support systems” were combined using Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT), and the search was filtered accordingly.

Several criteria were used to determine the publications to be included in the study. Accordingly, peer-reviewed studies published between 2015 and 2026, written in Turkish or English, related to the fields of health and education, and considered within the scope of AI literacy or DHL were included in the review. Studies for which the full text could not be accessed, studies focusing solely on AI algorithms, and studies that did not address human competencies were excluded.

The studies identified through the search were first screened at the title and abstract level. After duplicate records were removed, a preliminary assessment was conducted in accordance with the inclusion and exclusion criteria. At this stage, studies relevant to the aim of the research were identified, and 30 studies that directly contributed to the domains of AI literacy, digital health literacy, digital health competencies, health informatics, data literacy, and ethics-security were included in the core analysis pool. The studies in the core analysis pool were then examined at the full-text level, and the extracted data were analyzed using a thematic synthesis approach to develop the AI-supported DHL framework. Since this study did not involve data collection from human participants, ethics committee approval was not required.

3. Findings

As a result of the literature search, a total of 600 studies retrieved from the Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, and ERIC databases were assessed. The first 10 studies from each database, ranked by relevance, were included in the analysis pool. Following the preliminary assessment conducted at the title and abstract level, 154 studies were classified as included, 95 as pending, and 338 as excluded (Table 1).

Table 1.

Distribution of Records by Database		
Database	Number of records retrieved through the search	Number of records assessed
Scopus	1473	150
Web of Science	1270	150
PubMed	472	150
ERIC	435	150
Toplam	3650	600

Among the 600 records assessed, records with identical titles were checked, and 22 duplicate records were removed from the review pool. As a result, 578 studies were screened at the title and abstract level. Following the preliminary assessment (Table 2), 145 studies were marked as “included” because they were directly related to the aim of the study, 95 studies were

marked as “pending” because they required full-text review, and 338 studies were marked as “excluded” because they did not meet research criteria. The excluded studies generally focused only on the technical aspects of artificial intelligence and were not related to literacy.

Table 2.

Results of the Preliminary Assessment at the Title and Abstract Level After Duplicate Removal

Preliminary assessment status	Number of records
Total number of studies assessed	600
Duplicate studies	22
Unique studies	578
Studies labelled as included	145
Studies labelled as pending	95
Excluded studies	338

As a result of the preliminary assessment conducted based on titles and abstracts, 145 studies were found to be relevant to the research. However, 30 studies that were considered to provide the strongest contribution to the framework intended to be developed were

selected for the core analysis pool based on specific selection criteria (Table 3). In this regard, it can be stated that 145 studies constituted the screening pool, whereas the full-text review was conducted within the scope of the 30 core studies, and the findings were synthesized based on the studies in this core group.

Table 3.

Selection Criteria for Studies Included in the Core Analysis Pool

Selection criterion	Description
Direct relevance to the research topic	The study was related to AI literacy, digital health literacy, health informatics competencies, health data literacy, or clinical decision support systems.
Conceptual contribution	The study presented a framework, model, competency domain, scale dimension, or education structure.
Health context	The study was addressed in the context of healthcare professionals, health students, health informatics, or healthcare services.
Focus on human competencies	The study included dimensions related to human skills, literacy education, use, decision-making, or ethical evaluation, rather than focusing solely on technical algorithms.
Contribution to framework development	The study could be associated with at least one of the domains of the AI-supported DHL framework.

When the studies included in the core analysis pool were examined, they were found to concentrate on interrelated areas, including digital health literacy, digital health competencies, AI literacy in healthcare, eHealth literacy, health informatics competencies, and digital competencies in clinical practice. These studies provided the basis for structuring the AI-supported

DHL framework under the domains of digital health systems use, AI literacy, data and information literacy, critical evaluation, and ethics-security. The main characteristics of the studies included in the core analysis pool and their contributions to the AI-supported DHL framework are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Studies Included in the Core Analysis Pool and Their Contributions to the AI-supported DHL Framework

No	Study	Study type	Focus	Contribution to the AI supported DHL framework
1	Kim et. al. (2022) <i>Fundamentals of digital health literacy</i>	Scoping review	Core competencies of digital health literacy	Supports the traditional literacy, information literacy, media literacy, technology literacy, health literacy, and socioecological dimensions of DHL.
2	Tumuhimbise et al. (2025) <i>Enablers and challenges of integrating digital health into medical education curricula</i>	Scoping review	Integration of digital health into medical education curricula	Explains the integration of DHL into the education of healthcare professionals, including implementation barriers and facilitators.
3	Tudor Car et al. (2021) <i>Digital health training programs for medical students</i>	Scoping review	Digital health training programs for medical students	Show that digital health training programs are mostly elective, focused on a single domain, and limited in terms of assessment.
4	Brørs et al. (2023) <i>Among hospital health care providers</i>	Systematic review	eHealth literacy among hospital healthcare providers	Indicates that eHealth literacy should be addressed through the di-

				mension of individual skills, interaction with the system, and Access to the system.
5	Mainz et al. (2024) <i>Measuring the digital competence of health professionals</i>	Scoping review	Measurement of digital competence among health professionals	Shows that digital competence is a multidimensional construct consisting of technical, methodological, social, and personal dimensions.
6	Car et al. (2025) <i>The digital health competencies in medical education framework</i>	Delphi-based consensus study	Digital health competency framework	Presents a comprehensive digital health competency framework that includes professionalism, patient and population health, health information systems, and health data science.
7	Jimenes et al. (2020) <i>Digital health competencies for primary healthcare professionals</i>	Scoping review	Digital health competencies for primary healthcare professionals	Supports the need for competencies related to electronic health records, medical informatics, information technologies, and digital health education.
8	Nazeha et al. (2020) <i>A Digitally competent health workforce</i>	Scoping review	Digital competency frameworks for the healthcare workforce	Supports the dimensions of basic information technologies, health information management, digital communication, ethical and legal requirements, data security, and privacy.
9	Ferreira and Magalhaes (2026) <i>Instruments to assess the digital health competencies of healthcare professionals</i>	Scoping review	Instruments for assessing digital health competencies	Shows that multidimensional and psychometrically strong instruments for measuring digital health competencies are limited.
10	Longhini et al. (2022) <i>Digital health competencies among healthcare professionals</i>	Systematic review	Digital health competencies among healthcare professionals	Supports eHealth literacy, use of digital technologies, digital health knowledge, and psychological-emotional dimensions among healthcare professionals.
11	Özatkan and Şenel Tekin (2026) <i>Determinants of digital health literacy of healthcare professionals</i>	Systematic review	Determinants of digital health literacy among healthcare professionals	Identifies determinants of DHL such as educational level, professional experience, access to digital infrastructure, and technological competence.
12	Ye et al. (2026) <i>Exploring the status and influencing factors of nurses' digital health literacy</i>	Scoping review	Digital health literacy among nurses	Classifies nurses' digital health literacy levels, measurement tools, and influencing factors at individual, interpersonal, and organizational levels.
13	Ng et al. (2023) <i>Artificial intelligence education: An evidence-based medicine approach</i>	Conceptual /perspective article	Artificial intelligence education for healthcare professionals	Relates AI literacy to evidence-based medicine and clinical decision-making by classifying healthcare professionals as AI users, translators, and developers.
14	Malerbi et al. (2023) <i>Digital education for the deployment of artificial intelligence in health care</i>	Viewpoint	Digital education for AI applications in healthcare	Emphasizes that the safe implementation of AI requires education on the fundamentals of machine learning, dataset evaluation, clinical workflow, bias control, and ethical-legal dimensions.
15	El Arab et al. (2025) <i>Artificial intelligence in nursing</i>	Systematic review	AI attitudes, literacy, readiness, and adoption intention among nurses	Addresses AI literacy, self-efficacy, attitudes, anxiety, ethical/privacy concerns, and institutional support factors in an integrated manner.

16	Patel et al. (2026) <i>AI literacy among healthcare professionals and students in the Americas</i>	Viewpoint	AI literacy for healthcare professionals and students	Discusses AI literacy in relation to medical education, clinical decision support, regional inequalities, and health equity.
17	Buchgraber-Schnalzer et al. (2025) <i>cMOOC recommendations to enhance AI literacy among healthcare professionals</i>	Educational design/ experience report	Online AI literacy education for healthcare professionals	Shows that AI literacy can be enhanced through online learning environments and should be supported by ethical and legal discussions.
18	Uluğ et al. (2025) <i>Adaptation of the artificial intelligence literacy scale into Turkish</i>	Scale adaptation/ cross-sectional study	Turkish AI literacy scale	Provides a valid and reliable measurement tool for assessing AI literacy in the Turkish context.
19	Ali and Shaban (2026) <i>AI literacy in nursing education</i>	Mixed-methods study	AI literacy and ethical awareness in nursing education	Examines AI literacy, ethical awareness, and readiness for AI integration among nursing faculty members.
20	Çoban and Beydağ (2026) <i>Surgical nurses' artificial intelligence literacy and readiness levels</i>	Descriptive cross-sectional study	AI literacy and medical AI readiness among surgical nurses	Shows a strong positive relationship between AI literacy and medical AI readiness.
21	Kayser et al. (2022) <i>Health professionals' eHealth literacy and system experience before and after EHR Implementation</i>	Longitudinal study	eHealth literacy before and after EHR implementation	Demonstrates the importance of eHealth literacy, system experience, ease of use, and trust in the adoption of EHR systems.
22	Mather et al. (2022) <i>eHealth literacy of Australian undergraduate health profession students</i>	Descriptive cross-sectional study	eHealth literacy among undergraduate health profession students	Shows that digital health skills should be integrated into curricula health professions and that data security concerns are important.
23	Jin et al. (2026) <i>Mapping factors associated with nurses' attitudes toward artificial intelligence</i>	Scoping view	Factors influencing nurses' attitudes toward artificial intelligence	Classifies attitudes toward AI under demographic, cognitive, affective, behavioral, and external factors.
24	Kontodimopoulos et al. (2026) <i>Digital skills and readiness of Greek nurses for AI adoption</i>	Cross-sectional study	Digital skills and readiness for AI adoption among nurses	Shows a gap between general digital skills and readiness for AI, indicating the need for target AI education
25	Loutfy et al. (2026) <i>Digital proficiency: eHealth literacy and informatics competencies among nursing students</i>	Cross-sectional study	eHealth literacy and informatics competencies among nursing students	Reveals the relationship between eHealth literacy and nursing informatics competencies.
26	Moafa et al. (2026) <i>Nurses digital competency and test performance</i>	Cross-sectional study	Digital competency and task performance among nurses	Shows that digital competency is associated with job performance and work engagement.
27	Mikkonen et al. (2026) <i>Digital health competence among healthcare</i>	International cross-sectional cluster analysis	Digital health competence profiles among healthcare professionals	Classifies healthcare professionals' digital health competencies into profiles ranging from beginner to advanced levels.

	<i>professionals across 19 countries and regions</i>			
28	Stock et al. (2026) <i>Digital competencies of health professionals: German translation and content validation of digihealthcom and digicomlnf</i>	Translation and content validity study	Adaptation of digital health competency assessment instruments	Shows that the DigiHealthCom and DigiComLnf instruments can be used to assess individual and organizational digital competencies.
29	D'Agostino et al. (2026) <i>Measurement properties of instruments assessing digital competence in nursing</i>	Systematic review	Instruments for measuring digital competence in nursing	Evaluates the psychometric properties of instruments measuring nursing informatics, digital health, and information and communication technology competencies.
30	Lee et al. (2023) <i>Evaluating digital competencies for pharmacists</i>	Qualitative study	Digital competencies for pharmacists	Shows that profession-specific digital competency frameworks can be used for assessment and educational planning among healthcare professionals.

When the core studies presented in Table 4 are considered together, it becomes evident that AI-supported DHL cannot be addressed as a single area of knowledge or skill. The studies reviewed show that digital health literacy includes competencies such as using digital health systems, working with electronic health records, accessing and evaluating health information in digital environments. In addition, studies on AI literacy reveal that healthcare professionals need to understand the basic functioning of AI systems, question the accuracy of AI-generated outputs, and recognize ethical risks such as algorithmic bias and data security. Accordingly, as a result of the thematic synthesis, the AI-supported DHL framework was structured under five core domains: digital health systems literacy, AI literacy, data and information literacy, critical evaluation and use of decision support, and ethics, security, and privacy.

3.1. Digital Health Systems Literacy

The reviewed studies indicated that one of the core domains of AI-supported DHL is the competency to use digital health systems effectively. This domain includes competencies related to electronic health records, health information systems, telehealth applications, digital communication tools, and the management of digital patient data [5; 15; 16]. In addition, findings on the implementation of EHR systems show that not only technical Access but also system experience, ease of use, trust, and the level of eHealth literacy are influential in healthcare professionals' adoption of digital systems [17]. Therefore, digital health systems literacy was considered a foundational competency domain within the AI-supported DHL framework, upon which the other domains are built.

3.2 AI Literacy

The reviewed studies indicated that the second core domain of AI-supported DHL is AI literacy. This domain includes healthcare professionals' understanding of basic operating logic of AI systems, their appro-

priate use of AI-supported tools, and their critical evaluation of the outputs generated by these systems [18; 19]. Studies in the field of healthcare show that AI literacy is not limited to technical knowledge; rather, it also includes dimensions such as ethical awareness, algorithmic bias, data privacy, clinical safety, and human oversight [20; 21]. In addition, studies conducted with nurses and healthcare professionals indicate that as AI literacy increases, readiness for and the tendency to adopt medical AI applications also become stronger [22]. Therefore, AI literacy was considered a core competency domain within the AI-supported DHL framework, enabling healthcare professionals to use AI-supported digital systems safely, ethically, and consciously.

3.3. Data and Information Literacy

The third domain of the AI-supported DHL framework is data and information literacy. This domain includes healthcare professionals' competencies in accessing health information, understanding, managing, and interpreting data, and transforming it into usable knowledge in clinical decision-making processes [23; 24]. The inclusion of health information management, health data science, data security, and informatics competencies as core areas in digital health competency frameworks further strengthens the importance of this domain [15; 16]. Moreover, since the quality, accuracy, and clinical relevance of the data used in AI-supported systems are directly related to the reliability of AI-generated outputs, data and information literacy was considered one of the central components of the AI-supported DHL framework.

3.4. Critical Evaluation and Use of Decision Support

The reviewed studies indicate that another important domain of AI-supported digital health literacy is critical evaluation and the use of decision support. This domain includes healthcare professionals' ability to evaluate the information, recommendations, and outputs obtained from digital and AI-supported systems in

terms of accuracy, reliability, clinical appropriateness, and patient safety, rather than accepting them directly. In studies on AI literacy, technical understanding, critical evaluation, practical application, and ethical awareness are addressed as core components; healthcare professionals' readiness for medical AI is also considered to be related to these components [22; 25]. Similarly, studies on nursing informatics and digital health competencies show that information evaluation, informatics competence, and the ability to critically analyze digital solutions are necessary for digital data to be used in clinical decision-making processes [26; 27; 28]. Therefore, critical evaluation and the use of decision support were considered a core domain within the AI-supported DHL framework, enabling healthcare professionals to use digital and AI-based outputs consciously, safely, and in an evidence-based manner.

3.5. Ethics, Security, and Privacy

The reviewed studies indicate that the final domain of AI-supported DHL is ethics, security, and privacy. This domain includes healthcare professionals' competencies in protecting the confidentiality of patient data in digital health and AI applications, recognizing data security risks, and evaluating ethical issues such as algorithmic bias and data misuse. Studies conducted with health students and healthcare professionals show that the security of online health data, data privacy, and trust in digital systems are integral components of digital health literacy [29; 30]. Studies in the context of AI further demonstrate that ethical awareness, patient safety, algorithmic bias, human oversight, and institutional governance requirements are key determinants in the use of AI in healthcare [20; 21]. Therefore, ethics, security, and privacy were considered a core competency domain within the AI-supported DHL framework, enabling the safe, responsible, and patient-rights-oriented use of digital and AI-based healthcare applications.

When the five domains are considered together, AI-supported DHL appears to be a multidimensional construct that goes beyond the ability to use digital health systems and integrates AI knowledge, data and information management, critical evaluation, ethical sensitivity, and security awareness. This framework is therefore considered a holistic literacy domain that supports healthcare professionals' conscious, safe, and ethical participation in digital and AI-supported healthcare services.

4. Discussion

This study shows that AI-supported DHL cannot be explained solely by the ability to use digital tools; rather, it represents a multilayered competency area that integrates digital health systems, AI literacy, data and information literacy, critical use of decision support, and ethics-security dimensions. This finding is consistent with studies emphasizing that digital health competencies should be addressed beyond technical skills and in relation to information management, communication, ethical responsibility, patient safety, and professional decision-making processes [15; 16; 24].

The findings indicate that having basic knowledge of AI is not sufficient for healthcare professionals to benefit from AI-supported systems. It is also necessary

for them to evaluate the operating logic of these systems, their data-based limitations, the reliability of the outputs they generate, and their appropriateness to the clinical context. This is consistent with studies showing that AI education should include not only technical knowledge but also dimensions such as algorithmic bias, data security, ethical awareness, and human oversight [18; 19; 20].

The AI-supported DHL framework developed in this study establishes a conceptual bridge between digital health literacy and AI literacy. Although digital health competencies, eHealth literacy, health informatics, and AI literacy are often addressed as separate domains in the existing literature, the integration of AI with digital healthcare services requires these competencies to be considered together. Therefore, the AI-supported DHL framework indicates that education for healthcare professionals should go beyond tool use and the teaching of basic concepts and should also include practice-oriented competencies such as data literacy, critical evaluation, ethical decision-making, patient privacy, and the safe use of technology.

5. Conclusion

This study shows that DHL needs to be reconsidered in the age of AI. For healthcare professionals, the ability to use digital systems alone is no longer sufficient; they must also be able to evaluate the data produced by these systems, AI-generated outputs, ethical risks, and their impact on clinical decision-making processes together. Therefore, the AI-supported DHL framework proposed in this study indicates that healthcare professionals should take part in AI-supported healthcare services not only as users, but also as conscious evaluators and ethical decision-makers.

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